

FUNDAMENTALS OF PHARMACEUTICAL TERMINOLOGY AND THE DEGREE OF ITS APPLICATION IN MODERN PHARMACOLOGY

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Abstract. *This work covers methods of teaching the Latin language and the basis of pharmaceutical terminology and the extent of its application in modern pharmacology.*

The relevance of the topic is that teaching the Latin language at a medical university pursues a number of special goals, the essence of which boils down to the acquisition of knowledge about the Latin language, pharmaceutical terminology, the ability to translate Latin pharmaceutical terms, and the development of the student's personality

Key words: *pharmaceutical, treatment, medicine, chemical, pharmaceutical terminology, typical methods.*

Аннотация: *Данная работа освещает методы обучения латинскому языку и основе фармацевтической терминологии и степень её применения в современной фармакологии. Актуальность темы в том, что обучение латинскому языку в медицинском вузе преследует ряд специальных целей, сущность которых сводится к приобретению знаний о латинском языке, фармацевтической терминологии, умению переводить латинские фармацевтические термины, развитию личности студента.*

Ключевые слова: *фармацевтика, лечение, медицина, химия, фармацевтическая терминология, типичные методы.*

The word pharmaceutical comes from the Greek *pharmakon* (medicine). A number of special disciplines that comprehensively study the production and use of medicines of plant and mineral origin are included in a complex called pharmacy (from the Greek *Pharmakeia* - creation of medicines, treatment with medicines).

Terminology of disciplines that make up a complex called pharmaceutical terminology. One of its characteristic features is the traditional use of the Latin language.

Pharmacology is a science that studies the effect of drugs on the body. Under the basics of pharmaceutical terminology, it is necessary to understand, in addition to the range of general terminology issues, also special issues relating to individual sections of pharmaceutical terminology, botanical, chemical, pharmacological and other names.

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Modern pharmacy is based on a complex of scientific disciplines, the leading ones being pharmacology, pharmacognosy, pharmaceutical chemistry, pharmaceutical technology, biotechnology and some others.

The terminologies of the disciplines that make up this complex interpenetrate, create intersystem connections with each other and form as a whole a terminological complex called pharmaceutical terminology.

The traditional use of the Latin language for practical and scientific problems is one of the remarkable features of both pharmacy and medicine. Nomenclature names occupy a predominant place in pharmaceutical terminology.

Subject and object of work. The object of research in this case is the theoretical justification of the process of mastering the Latin language and pharmaceutical terminology. Representatives of the direction study concepts, forms of education, content of educational programs, and mechanisms for their design.

The purpose and objectives of the work. Along with this, modern linguists consider their most important task to be the implementation of the integrative function: the unification of philosophical, psychological, linguistic, and pedagogical theories in order to create conditions for the most effective learning process.

Theoretical and practical significance of the work. Terminology, as a reflection of a person's professional activity in a particular field of knowledge, consolidates the information obtained as a result of this activity in the system of linguistic signs, creating an idea of one of the fragments of the scientific picture of the world.

The basics of pharmaceutical terminology mean the following:

- 1) The concept of a scientific term and nomenclature name; about the nomenclatures included in the complex "Pharmaceutical Terminology";
- 2) The principles of constructing the various nomenclatures that make up this complex;
- 3) Synonymy of drugs and its causes;
- 4) Typical methods for creating nomenclature names
- 5) Signs of a pharmacological, therapeutic, chemical nature, reflected in the names of medicines.

Conclusion. Research of pharmaceutical terminology is an extremely relevant area of pharmaceutical science. The results of such research are necessary and important for all types of pharmaceutical activities - scientific, practical and educational, including the use of modern information technologies.

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